

APPENDIX – Interviews Professionals DSD: Technical Report

The empirical research is centered in the choice of aspects of the relation between subjects. It aims the process of interaction and face-to-face, that is, the researcher cannot elaborate the research “in laboratory” or in a library isolated with only books around him. In this modality of the knowledge elaboration, the researcher must “go to the field”.

The empirical study with 31 professionals was developed in twelve units of software development companies. The objective of this study was to understand the challenges of the communication, identify the factors with more priority, as well as the communication practices adopted in the DSD context. The research participants were geographically distributed as follows: One professional was located in Canada, five in the United States, and Twenty-five in Brazil, in the following states: Paraíba, Pernambuco, Rio Grande do Sul e São Paulo. An effort was made to understand the relevance order of the factors, as well as classify them in maturity levels to the conception of the first version of the C2M model.

1 SELECTION OF THE ORGANIZATION AND UNITIES OF ANALYSIS

The unit of analysis of the study was defined as being professionals of organizations involved in DSD projects.

Professionals of twelve organizations were selected (C1, C2, C3, C4, C5, C6, C7, C8, C9, C10, C11 e C12), and they all provided their professionals with unrestricted access to the questioned information. Some organizations only liberated the professionals to the interview after the signature of a confidentiality agreement. In the Section 4 the results found in the empirical research in this step are detailed.

2 DATA SOURCE AND SELECTION OF THE PARTICIPANTS

The data collection was conducted by primary sources. The primary sources were constituted by interviews. Were performed 12 semi-structured in-depht interviews. They started with a basic script with questions formulated to the

interviewed and adjusted according to its conduction. The table 1 shows the time spent with the data collection in every company.

Table 1 - Data collection time.

Company	Interview Time	Number of interviewed people	Language
C1	1h 15 min	1	Portuguese
C2	1h 05 min	1	
C3	1h 30 min	1	
C4	1h 05 min	1	
C5	1h 15 min	1	
C6	1h 25 min	1	
C7	3h	2	
C8	1h	1	
C9	1h	1	
C10	2h 35 min	2	
C11	9h 30 min	10	
C12	8h 20min	9	
Total	33h	31	

Source: the author

In the beginning of the study, every professional was invited and the agreement of the organizations they work to the participation in the research was asked. Every professional in accordance with the organization answered the invite with the acceptance to make part of the research. However, some companies demanded a confidentiality term to liberate the professional to the interviews. All the interviews were recorded and transcript with the authorization of the professionals

The initial criterion to the definition of the respondents was centered mainly in the objectives of the study. In this sense, the population direct or indirectly involved was constituted mainly of collaborators in two levels: management and operational. In the management level, was sought the vision of managers with knowledge sufficient to respond questions about the project management in the DSD context and the interaction between unities and/or subsidiaries (if they exist). In the operational level, was sought the vision of the technical leaders and software developers, with enough knowledge to answer questions about the several projects developed in the company they work.

3 DATA COLLECTION TOOLS

The data collection tools consisted of a script to semi-structured interviews, with open and non-inductive questions. The interviews were organized to identify challenges, main communication factors of the technical and non-technical parts.

4 DATA ANALYSIS

In relation to the data analysis, all the interviews were recorded, transcript and after analyzed, through content analysis according to Coutinho (2005). At first, the data was prepared; after the transcriptions, a careful reading was performed, seeking the familiarization of the researcher with the data before starting the codification of the categories. Next, the texts were codified, following two steps.

The first step involved the classification of a subset of the texts in one of the following categories: maturity factors of the communication and good practices in DSD communication (Figure 1).

Figure 1 - Data analysis. Source: the author

Microsoft Excel and the Weft QDA (<http://www.pressure.to/qda/>) were used as data analysis tools.

5 CONDUCTION OF THE STUDY

The research performed with the thirty-one respondents of the twelve organizations allowed to develop the proposed study as planned. It involved the contacts, aiming to develop the in-depth interviews, and the organizations, which made available the physical space conditions and the support to the research. The linking of this research with the GP2 group, of the Federal University of Pernambuco – UFPE helped this process.

In the organizations, the contact occurred between the researcher and the collaborators of the organizations. After this initial contact, was performed a meeting to present the protocol of the study and obtain the approval to perform it. With the approval obtained, was possible begin the research and execute the interviews.

The research tool (semi-structured script) was developed based on an initial script of questions, parting from the theory studied and represented in the research protocol developed for the study. Successive refinements were performed until the partial version of the script. Then, the validation of face and content was performed by two senior researchers (doctors), one in Rio Grande do Sul and other in Pernambuco.

The next activity was the execution of the pilot of the interviews, also known as pre-test. Two interviews were performed; one with a project manager directly involved in DSD projects with national dispersion level and other with a software developer with global dispersion level. With the application of the pilot, was possible to discover the weaknesses and eliminate ambiguities, choosing also the formulation of the questions most coherent to the research objective. Before the interviews, adjusts in the script were done and, next, the final version of it was defined to carry on the study. After the adjust of the instrument based in the pre-test, the interview phase started.

Interviews with thirty-one professionals were defined, selected by convenience. All the interviews were previously scheduled and transcribed after they occurred. Aiming to ensure the quality of the data, six respondents were contacted again to clarify some points where the researcher had doubts.

With the transcriptions in hands, was done the qualitative analysis of the data. At first, was performed an analysis of the content, where were defined the preliminary categories. This process was developed by the researcher and after consolidated with the Adviser and co-Adviser, defining a set of categories to be considered.

6 RESULTS OF THE STUDY

The participants were managers, leaders and software developers acting in DSD projects. In the beginning of the interviews, were obtained information about the academic formation, experience in DSD projects, among other information. The participants were selected in function of their roles in the project.

The respondents have, in average, 6 years of experience in DSD. The average age was 36 years, being the minimal age 27 years, and the maximum age 54 years. Most of the respondents have between 30 and 40 years. The interviews lasted an

average of 1h 04 minutes and counted with total availability and attention of the participants. About the dispersion level of the projects, 52% were classified as Global, and 48% as National (Figure 2).

Figure 2 - Types of dispersion of the projects. Source: the author.

The information was provided always respecting the privacy and confidentiality policies of the project they were involved. In relation to the formation level, all the interviewed are from the computing area, and post-graduated. On the table 2, more details are presented.

Table 2 - profile and distribution of the respondents.

Company(C)	Respondents (R)	Area of Work	Experiência em DSD	Nível de Dispersão
C1	R1	Software Developer	9 years	National
C2	R2	Software Developer	8 years	National
C3	R3	Project Manager	4 years	National
C4	R4	Project Manager	3 years	National
C5	R5	Project Manager	6 years	National
C6	R6	Technical Leader	8 years	National
C7	R7	Project Manager	10 years	Global
	R8	Software Developer	5 years	Global
C8	R9	Software Developer	3 years	Global
C9	R10	Project Manager	3 years	Global
C10	R11	Project Manager	4 years	Global
	R12	Software Developer	3 years	Global
C11	R14	Project Manager	7 years	National
	R15	Project Manager	5 years	National
	R16	Project Manager	7 years	National
	R17	Test Analyst	5 years	National
	R18	Test Analyst	4 years	National
	R19	Software Developer	9 years	National

	R20	Software Developer	6 years	National
	R21	Software Developer	4 years	National
	R22	Software Developer	3 years	National
C12	R23	Technical Leader	8 years	Global
	R24	Technical Leader	8 years	Global
	R25	Technical Leader	6 years	Global
	R26	Project Manager	7 years	Global
	R27	Project Manager	7 years	Global
	R28	Project Manager	3 years	Global
	R29	Test Analyst	9 years	Global
	R30	Test Analyst	8 years	Global
	R31	Test Analyst	8 years	Global

Source: the author

7 TOOLS USED IN DSD PROJETCS

The graph represented by the Figure 33 shows the intensity of use of the communication tools in the DSD projects. The question whose answers resulted in this graph permitted the participants to cite the tools used in communication on the DSD projects they participated. In the figure 3, is possible to realize that e-mail and telephone still are the most used communication tools in DSD projects.

Figure 3 - Tools used in DSD Projects. Source: the author

The participants of this study affirmed that most of the tools used in their projects are proprietary. 22 respondents said that the DSD projects where they work used mainly paid tools, because of their maturity for the professional use.

Furthermore, the participants said that in the companies where they worked or work with DSD the used tools were often mature (with more than 3 years of market).

8 FACTORS WHICH AFFECT THE COMMUNICATION IN DSD PROJECTS

According to the analysis of the collected data, can be said that the factors (considered challenges) of the DSD communication, according to the 31 respondents of the 12 companies, are centered in the absence of the understanding of the activities, absence of mechanisms (guides, processes, models) to the planning of the communication in projects, lack of standardization of the activities between the distributed teams and the absence of a well-defined process reflecting in the requirement engineering activities. Plus, also were verified factors in relation to language barriers, cultural differences, among other (Table 3).

Table 3 - Factors identified in the empirical study.

Communication Factors	Respondents (R)
Provide project results to the high management	R1, R2, R4, R5, R6, R9, R10, R11, R12,R13,R20,R22,R30
Requirement Elicitation and Specification	R1, R2, R3, R4, R5, R8, R10,R20,R31
Frequent Videoconference Meetings	R1, R2, R4, R5, R6, R7,R14,R16,R22,R27
Trust Building	R1,R2, R3, R4, R8, R9, R11,R15,R16,R18,R19,R20,R21,R22,R23,R24,R25,26
Communication Planning	R1, R2, R4, R5, R6,R12,R19,R20,R24,R25,R27,R30
Management of Cultural Differences	R3, R4, R8, R9, R18,R19,R20,R22,R31
Interpersonal Relations	R3,R4, R8, R9, R9,R15, R16,R22,R25,R26,R28,R30R,31
Create focal points (ambassadors) in every remote team.	R2, R3, R5, R7, R8, R10, R14, R21, R25, R27, R28, R29
Continuous Communication Improvement	R2, R3, R8, R12
Communication Policies and Practices	R2, R5, R11, R20,R23,R27,R29
Definition of communication support tools.	R1, R2, R3,R4,R7,R10,R14,R29
Understanding of the provided information	R2, R8,R13,R20,R25,R29,R31
Synchronous communication	R6,R7,R12,R13,R14,R15,R16,R17,R18R20,R25,R26,R27,R28
Definition of a default language	R1,R3,R4,R5,R10,R11,R12,R15,R28,R29,R30,R31
Knowledge Management	R6, R8, R10, R19, R21
Communication Infrastructure	R1,R3,R5,R6,R7,R12,R15,R16,R17,R18R20,R21,R25,R26,R27,R28
Information and Task Distribution	R2,R5,R11,R12,R21,R20,R21,R23,R25,R30,R31
Asynchronous Communication	R1,R3,R5,R6,R7,R12,R13,R14,R15,R16,R17,R18R20,R21,R25,R26,R27, R28

Human Resource Allocation Planning in Projects	R13,R14,R15,17,R18
Training to develop communication abilities	R1,,R6,R7,R12,R13,R14,R15,R16,R17,R18R20,R21,R25,R26,R27,R28
Standardization of the terminologies/vocabular used in the Project	R10,R12,R20,R22,R29
Configuration management	R10,R12,R20,R22,R29
Face-to-face Interaction	R3, R4, R8,R9,R15, R16,R22,R25,R26,R28,R30R,31
Determine the communication channel	R3, R4, R8, R9,R15, R16,R22,R25,R26,R28
Manage the stakeholders	R3, R4, R8, R9, R18,R19,R20,R22,R31
Interchange between team members	R1,R2,R3,R10,,R19,R20,R21,R22,R23,R24,R25
Conflict management	R12,R13,R16,R18,R20
Temporal Distance Management (Time zone)	R5, R6, R9, R10, R11, R12,R13,R14,R15,R19,R20,R21
Synchronization of the work schedules	R1,R2,R3,R10,R13,R16,R19,R20,R21,R22,R23,R24,R25,R26,28
Leadership Style	R1,R2,R3,R10,,R19,R20,R21,R22,R23,R24,R25
Activities Standardization	R1, R2, R4, R5, R6, R7,R14,R16,R22,R27
Cordiality between the stakeholders	R3, R7, R8, R9, R12, R15,R29,R30
Management of the meeting schedule	R5, R6, R9, R10, R11, R12,R13,R14,R15,R19,R20,R22,R30

Source: The author.

The identification of the communication factors is directly linked to the work method of a certain organization. Different factors can exist to the same activity, each one, linked to the adopted strategy. Aiming to consolidate the results were explicated the most relevant ones in the view of the respondent (Table 4).

Table 4 - Communication Factors in relevance order.

Communication Factors	Is the fator Relevant?	(%)
	Yes	
To provide results of the project to the high management	31	100%
Requirement Elicitation and Specification	31	100%
Frequent Communication	31	100%
Trust Acquisition	31	100%
Communication Planning	31	100%
Management of Cultural Differences	31	100%
Interpersonal Relationship	31	100%
Continuous Improvement of the Management	30	97%
Communication Policies and Patterns	29	94%
Definition of communication support tools	29	94%
Understanding of the provided information	29	94%

Ability to elicitate and negotiate requirements with the cliente	28	90%
Synchronous Communication	27	87%
Definition of a default Language	27	87%
Knowledge management	27	87%
Communication Infrastructure	26	84%
Information and task distribution	26	84%
Asynchronous Communication	26	84%
Planning of the human resource alocation in projects	26	84%
Training to develop communication abilities	26	84%
Standardization of the terminologies/vocabulary used in the Project	25	81%
Configuration Management	25	81%
Face-to-face Interaction	25	81%
Determine the communication channel	22	71%
Manage the stakeholders	22	71%
Interchange between team members	22	71%
Conflict management	22	71%
Temporal Distance Management (Time Zone)	20	65%
Synchronization of the Work schedules	20	65%
Leadership Style	19	61%
Activity Standardization	19	61%

Source: the author

From the exposed on Table 19, we can realize that, of the 31 factors that were found, 11 vary between 94% and 100% of relevance according to the opinion of the respondents. These factors are considered of major impact for DSD projects from the point of view of those who deal daily with distributed software projects. Aiming to corroborate with this affirmation, some passages extracted from the interviews with the referred answerers are shown above:

- **Supply the High Management with results of the project:** For the respondent 22 *“the high management is represented by the project manager.”* However, the respondent 28 said *“that the information of the project have to be passed on and presented to the high management periodically so the high management can be aware of everything that occurs in the project. Still to this respondent, this type of monitoring can be done in the points of control (“Project marks”) planned on the schedule of the projects.”*
- **Elicitation and Specification of the requirements:** For the respondent 6 the *“specification and elicitation of the requirements is a highly communicative activity, which means it is necessary for the*

professional that will perform this activity to be a good speaker, a skilled writer and know the subject in the technical aspect.” The respondent 6 also said *“that this type of professional is hard to find in the market.”* But respondent 19 said *“that this activity requires a lot of attention in traditional projects. When this same activity is performed in DSD projects, it is necessary to double the attention to minimize or avoid errors that can generate rework.”*

- **Frequent communication:** The respondents 4 and 5 said that with the adoption of agile practices it is simple to solve this (for example, daily meetings, reviews, retrospectives and etc). The answerer 27 says *“it is necessary to create means of communication in many levels. For example: forums for discussion among teams, meetings to present the results with the high administration of the organization, meetings to resolution of technical problems and etc.”*
- **Acquisition of trust:** The respondent 11 says *“that trust comes from the good relationship with everyone in the Project, as well as from a good workplace.”* However, respondent 5 says *“that an effective communication generates trust among the collaborators.”* Then respondent 9 says *“it is necessary to create moments of integration to break the barrier among the members of the teams and then the trust building among them happens naturally. “*
- **Managing cultural differences:** The respondent 15 was very emphatic to say *“that this is a vital point to be managed in distributed projects.”* However, the answerer 23 says *“that culture is difficult to be managed when people are in the same state or country. When the teams are globally distributed, it gets much more complicated.”* The respondent 3 corroborates *“the relevance of the culture when he says that cultural problems that occur in traditional projects are even more serious in DSD projects, since they cause a diminution of the face to face interaction.”*
- **Communication planning:** The respondent 13 says *“that this practice must be mandatory in any type of project.”* But the respondent 22 says *“that it is necessary to create an organizational culture to indoctrinate the collaborators to plan the communication in their projects systematically.”* At last, the respondent 13 says *“that the communication*

is one of the areas that lead projects to failure. And as such it is necessary to manage the communication from the start to the end of the project so the level of communication can be evaluated and good practices can be replicated in other projects.”

- **Continuous improvement of the communication:** The respondent 30 emphasizes that *“the communication is the backbone of any organization or project.”* To support this affirmation, the respondent 23 says that *“people who communicate better are able to transcend effectively when problems arise. He also says that we need to review the policy and planning of communication, seeking its continuous improvement.”* But respondent 29 says that *“there is no formula to deal with communication. It is necessary that we have a system to reflect upon the communication in each and every project continuously.”*
- **Interpersonal relationship:** The respondent 11 says that *“a good interpersonal relationship brings more trust to the teams.”* But the respondent 25 goes *“deeper on the matter and paraphrases a Chinese proverb that says the following: if you want 1 year of prosperity, grow grain. If you want 10 years of prosperity, grow trees. If you want 100 years of prosperity, grow people.”*
- **Policies and patterns of communication:** The respondent 1 says that *“it is necessary to create policies and patterns to reach the excellence.”* Then respondent 10 says that *“organizational policy is something necessary, however, when the organization does not have a well-defined culture it is necessary to be careful so that it won’t end up getting in the way of the management/operationalization of the project instead of helping.”*
- **Definition of tools that support the communication:** Respondent 22 says that *“there is no successful project without planning. And in the context of projects with distributed teams, such planning must contemplate the definition of the tools that are used for communication. In case that doesn’t happen, huge problems may occur during the project.”*
- **Understanding of the provided information:** Respondent 5: Often, *“the teams don’t have the same understanding of what is being developed*

as a whole, what causes many misunderstandings about the concept of the project.” Supporting this affirmation, the respondent 6 says that “in every project there will be misunderstood information, however, it is necessary to create mechanisms to minimize and sometimes even avoid that this come to happen in the projects. There are enterprises that establish goals and errors that come from wrong information.”

In this sense, it was identified through the reported information by the answerer the area where the communication efforts in DSD projects are more concentrated (Figure 4).

Figure 4 - Communication effort in DSD per phase. Source: the author.